

BioSCape combines local knowledge and remote sensing technology for inclusive biodiversity science

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Standfirst

The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape) in South Africa's Greater Cape Floristic Region aims to test the limits and potential of remote sensing for biodiversity applications. Integrating field biodiversity measurements and local knowledge with advanced remote sensing, BioSCape brings us closer to measuring key biodiversity variables globally from space.

Main Text

Addressing biodiversity loss, which jeopardizes human wellbeing and sustainable development, is the target of global conservation and human development goals¹. Tracking progress towards these goals requires biodiversity data at a scale and latency not feasible for traditional field observations alone. Remote sensing can augment field data, and emerging developments including satellite-borne radar, light detection and ranging (LiDAR), and imaging spectroscopy have enhanced what can be observed from above. However, because ecosystem properties can be highly site-specific, many biodiversity variables of interest cannot be captured with remote sensing data exclusively². To observe the idiosyncrasies of an ecosystem at spatial and temporal scales necessary to monitor and manage biodiversity, field and remote sensing data sets must be integrated³.

Advancing the capability of these integrated data sets to measure, monitor, and explain patterns and drivers of biodiversity across diverse ecosystems is an urgent priority in the face of the global biodiversity crisis. NASA's first-ever field campaign focussing on terrestrial, freshwater, and marine biodiversity — the Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape) — combines local knowledge with global remote sensing technology to produce openly accessible data products. In this Comment, we introduce BioSCape and emphasize the importance of integrated data and inclusive international collaboration for biodiversity conservation globally.

42 BioSCape

43 BioSCape is an integrated remote sensing and field campaign conducted in the Greater Cape
44 Floristic Region (GCFR) of South Africa in October and 2023. The GCFR spans eight
45 terrestrial and six marine biomes, hosts two of the world's richest biodiversity hotspots, and has
46 exceptional levels of terrestrial and aquatic endemism⁴. Biodiversity in the GCFR is threatened
47 by factors including drought, invasive plants, changes to ocean chemistry and currents, and
48 complex pressures from human populations⁵⁻⁷. The GCFR is a microcosm of global challenges
49 — a highly biodiverse region that must support sustainable human development while surviving
50 the threat of climate change. Fortunately, the region has a long history of data-informed
51 conservation and provides learning opportunities that can inform management of similar regions
52 worldwide⁸.

53 Integrated data to measure biodiversity

54 During BioSCape, airborne imaging spectroscopy (also known as hyperspectral remote
55 sensing) and LiDAR data were acquired over terrestrial, freshwater and marine study areas.
56 Imaging spectroscopy measures reflected and emitted solar radiation at high spectral resolution,
57 enabling the retrieval of biodiversity information such as mapping aquatic primary producers or
58 leaf functional traits^{9,10}. In combination with LiDAR measurements of the three-dimensional
59 structure of terrestrial ecosystems, imaging spectroscopy data provide further opportunities for
60 remote sensing of biodiversity, such as classifying tree species¹¹. BioSCape's airborne data set,
61 achieved using three imaging spectrometers and two LiDAR instruments, provides
62 unprecedented detail by covering much of the ultraviolet (UV), visible to shortwave infrared
63 (VSWIR), and thermal infrared (TIR) ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum and coincident
64 LiDAR acquisitions. This combined spectral and structural airborne data set is necessary to
65 explore the potential of satellite remote sensing for measuring and monitoring global
66 biodiversity¹².

67
68 BioSCape's airborne data set is accompanied by field measurements on land and in water.
69 Field data were collected by 19 individually funded PI-led research projects, each with its own
70 objectives including: mapping marine and freshwater biodiversity, including phytoplankton, kelp,
71 and harmful algal blooms; quantifying how changes in ocean chemistry and sea-level rise
72 associated with climate change will affect aquatic ecosystems, specifically estuaries and kelp
73 forests; mapping terrestrial ecosystem properties including evapotranspiration, plant traits,
74 vegetation 3D structure, and mineralogy; quantifying spatial variation and drivers of plant
75 community assembly and ecosystem function, including alien plant invasions; and combining
76 novel field methods, including eDNA and acoustic indices, with remotely sensed data to
77 estimate the composition and diversity of biotic communities.

78
79 BioSCape's research projects all aim to better understand the structure, function, and
80 composition of the GCFR's ecosystems, and to learn how and why they are changing in time
81 and space. These diverse projects will integrate and analyze remote sensing and field data, and
82 advance models and algorithms for measuring and monitoring biodiversity at multiple scales. By
83 combining satellite, airborne, and field-based measurements, BioSCape aims to expand the

84 capacity of integrated data sets to produce accurate and scalable findings and help improve
85 conservation efficacy. High species richness and endemism in the GCFR, combined with open
86 and often scrubby vegetation, make remote sensing particularly challenging. BioSCape will be
87 testing the limits and potential of remote sensing for biodiversity applications worldwide. As a
88 team member noted, “if we can do it in the GCFR, we can do it anywhere.”

89 Inclusive Collaboration for Increased Impact

90 Applying global perspectives and technology in local contexts requires international
91 collaboration, which can bring benefits including increased scientific impact and applicability¹³.
92 However, international collaboration can be challenging as countries can have different skills
93 and access to resources. In such cases, extra care must be taken to ensure the collaboration is
94 inclusive and benefits everyone involved.

95
96 Since its conception, BioSCape has emphasized creating and maintaining deep and meaningful
97 collaboration between U.S. and South African researchers, and the importance of co-developing
98 research. Early inclusion of South African researchers in the design of airborne and field
99 components of BioSCape led to a diverse team of ~150 members, of which approximately half
100 are affiliated with South African institutions and half with U.S. institutions. U.S. participation
101 ensured global applicability and access to best-in-class technology, and bridged gaps in
102 capacity. South African expertise ensured that the research agenda for BioSCape was locally
103 relevant and that local ecological expertise was incorporated.

104
105 As biodiversity is intrinsically site-specific, effective conservation hinges on local knowledge and
106 region-specific actions. In the GCFR, strong personal and institutional relationships among
107 research institutes, environmental management authorities and conservation managers have
108 yielded rapid dissemination and uptake of novel science relevant to decision-making. South
109 Africa is a well-known early adopter of systematic conservation planning, has been relatively
110 successful in operationalizing conservation planning into government policy and decision-
111 making, and has ‘set the standard’ for using scientific information in conservation planning and
112 implementation^{8,14}. Therefore, data products created by BioSCape will inform biodiversity
113 conservation, environmental decision-making and policy in South Africa, and guide the
114 management of similar ecosystems worldwide⁴ (**FIGURE 1**).

115 Conclusion

116 The GCFR’s megadiversity, established pathway from science to application, and diverse
117 threats to biodiversity are a microcosm of global biodiversity challenges and opportunities. As
118 satellite acquisitions of rich, highly dimensional data types improve in area coverage, spatial
119 resolution, and temporal latency in the coming years, BioSCape provides a proof of concept for
120 remote sensing of biodiversity using imaging spectroscopy and LiDAR combined with several
121 complementary field techniques. Although some of BioSCape’s planned approaches might fail,
122 we expect they will teach us almost as much about the remote sensing of biodiversity as the
123 successes, not to mention the serendipitous discoveries.

124

126
 127 **Figure 1:**
 128 “Biodiversity observations inform conservation management decisions when developed with
 129 local stakeholders” Measuring and monitoring biodiversity variables in campaigns such as
 130 BioSCape can directly impact biodiversity conservation. For example, in South Africa,
 131 biodiversity observations can be processed to produce relevant data products that are used to
 132 inform biodiversity assessment, planning, and reporting, directly affecting biodiversity policy and
 133 conservation management decisions (which, in turn, inform observation approaches and
 134 product development). For this reason, the most impactful biodiversity research projects are co-
 135 designed with local stakeholders.
 136

137 **References**

138 1. Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity. 15/5. Monitoring
 139 framework for the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. (2022).
 140 2. Cavender-Bares, J. et al. Integrating remote sensing with ecology and evolution to advance
 141 biodiversity conservation. *Nat Ecol Evol* 6, 506–519 (2022).
 142 3. Turner, W. Sensing biodiversity. *Science* 346, 301–302 (2014).
 143 4. Skowno, A. et al. National Biodiversity Assessment 2018: The status of South Africa’s
 144 ecosystems and biodiversity. Synthesis Report. Synthesis Report. South African National
 145 Biodiversity Institute, an entity of the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries,
 146 Pretoria. (2019).
 147 5. James, N. et al. Effects of climate change on South African estuaries and associated fish
 148 species. *Clim. Res.* 57, 233–248 (2013).
 149 6. Slingsby, J. A. et al. Intensifying postfire weather and biological invasion drive species loss in
 150 a Mediterranean-type biodiversity hotspot. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 114, 4697–4702 (2017).

- 151 7. Sydeman, W. J. et al. Climate change and wind intensification in coastal upwelling
152 ecosystems. *Science* 345, 77–80 (2014).
- 153 8. Balmford, A. Conservation planning in the real world: South Africa shows the way. *Trends in*
154 *Ecology & Evolution* 18, 435–438 (2003).
- 155 9. Hestir, E., Dronova, I., & University of California, Berkeley. Remote Sensing of Primary
156 Producers in the Bay-Delta. *SFEWS* 20, (2023).
- 157 10. Wang, Z. et al. Foliar functional traits from imaging spectroscopy across biomes in eastern
158 North America. *New Phytologist* 228, 494–511 (2020).
- 159 11. Naidoo, L., Cho, M. A., Mathieu, R. & Asner, G. Classification of savanna tree species, in
160 the Greater Kruger National Park region, by integrating hyperspectral and LiDAR data in a
161 Random Forest data mining environment. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote*
162 *Sensing* 69, 167–179 (2012).
- 163 12. Dierssen, H. M. et al. Synergies Between NASA’s Hyperspectral Aquatic Missions PACE,
164 GLIMR, and SBG: Opportunities for New Science and Applications. *JGR Biogeosciences* 128,
165 e2023JG007574 (2023).
- 166 13. Choi, H. & Oh, D. The importance of research teams with diverse backgrounds: Research
167 collaboration in the *Journal of Productivity Analysis*. *J Prod Anal* 53, 5–19 (2020).
- 168 14. Buschke, F. T., Botts, E. A. & Sinclair, S. P. Post-normal conservation science fills the space
169 between research, policy, and implementation. *Conservat Sci and Prac* 1, e73 (2019).

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199 **Competing interests**

200 The authors declare no competing interests

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